

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF HEAVY METAL ACCUMULATION IN THE LEAVES OF WOODY SPECIES IN URBAN CONDITIONS OF BAKU, AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

This study investigates the accumulation of heavy metals - zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), lead (Pb), and cadmium (Cd) - in the leaf tissues of *Quercus ilex* L. and *Olea europaea* L. growing in different urban environments of Baku, Azerbaijan. Samples were collected from both a relatively clean area and zones exposed to traffic and industrial pollution. Metal concentrations were measured using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy. *Quercus ilex* showed higher accumulation of Cu and Pb, indicating greater sensitivity to pollution and suitability as a bio-indicator. *Olea europaea* exhibited lower leaf concentrations, suggesting better physiological resistance. These findings highlight the role of evergreen trees in urban environmental monitoring and the value of selecting sensitive species for sustainable city planning.

Keywords: heavy metals, leaf, bioaccumulation, *O. europaea*, *Q. ilex*

Introduction. Since the second half of the 20th century, rapid scientific and technological advancement has significantly accelerated industrialization and urbanization across the globe. While this progress has contributed to improvements in economic development and quality of life, it has also led to a profound deterioration of environmental quality (Mammadova A. et al., 2024; Maharram et al., 2025). One of the most pressing consequences of intensified anthropogenic activity is the widespread pollution of natural ecosystems, particularly in urban areas. Among various pollutants, heavy metals are of special concern due to their non-biodegradable nature, high toxicity, and ability to bioaccumulate and biomagnify through food chains (Pan et al., 2018; Nasirova et al., 2022)

Heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu) enter the urban environment through multiple sources, including emissions from vehicles and industrial facilities, fossil fuel combustion, atmospheric fallout, and the improper disposal of industrial and municipal waste (Cimboláková et al., 2019). Once released into the environment, these elements can persist in soils, water bodies, and vegetation for extended periods, posing serious risks to both ecological systems and public health. Long-term exposure to elevated levels of heavy metals is associated with a range of adverse effects, including neurotoxicity, mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, and disruptions to the functioning of plant and microbial communities (Mamedova, 2020; Mammadzada et al., 2025).

In recent decades, growing attention has been paid to the role of urban green spaces and vegetation as both bioindicators and biological filters of environmental pollution (Mamedova, 2009; Nazim & Oqtay, 2024). Tree species, due to their longevity, large leaf area, and stable location, are particularly useful for monitoring spatial variations in air and soil pollution levels. Their leaves act as passive samplers, accumulating pollutants. By analyzing the concentrations of heavy metals in leaf

tissues, it is possible to assess the intensity and distribution of urban contamination without resorting to destructive or costly sampling methods (Mammadova R. & Mammadova A, 2020; Ismayilova et al., 2025).

Considering all of the above, the aim of our research was to compare the accumulation of heavy metals - specifically Pb, Cd, Zn, and Cu - in the leaves of *Olea europaea* L. and *Quercus ilex* L. trees growing in different parts of Baku (Azerbaijan). By identifying which species tend to accumulate higher concentrations of these metals and determining the areas with the most severe pollution, this study aims to support more informed urban planning, enhance environmental monitoring efforts, and contribute to the development of green spaces that can actively mitigate air pollution.

Materials and methods. This study focuses on two evergreen tree species commonly found in Mediterranean and semi-arid regions - European olive (*Olea europaea* L.) and Holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L.). Both species were selected as objects of investigation due to their ecological adaptability, ornamental value, and relevance for urban landscaping in the climatic conditions of Baku (Mammadova et al., 2017).

O. europaea is an evergreen tree belonging to the family *Oleaceae*. It typically reaches a height of 4 to 10 meters, with a gnarled trunk and a rounded or irregular crown. The leaves are leathery, narrow, lanceolate, and silver-green, contributing to its high decorative and cultural value. The species is well adapted to drought and calcareous soils, tolerates salinity. While sensitive to prolonged frost, olive trees perform well in urban conditions and are commonly used in landscaping and roadside plantings in warm climates. Their leaf surface provides a suitable substrate for the accumulation and analysis of airborne pollutants, including heavy metals (Turan et al., 2011).

Q. ilex is a large, long-lived, evergreen tree in the family *Fagaceae*, growing up to 20–25 meters in height. It features a dense, rounded crown and thick,

leathery leaves with a dark green upper surface and pale underside. Young leaves often display spiny or toothed margins, contributing to the species' distinct "spiky" appearance. The Holm oak is highly valued in urban environments for its aesthetic appearance, tolerance to drought, and resistance to frost (down to -15°C), pollution, and poor soils. It adapts well to urban stressors such as soil compaction, road dust, and dry conditions, making it an effective bioindicator and a reliable candidate for urban greening and environmental monitoring (Misson et al., 2010).

The research was conducted within the urban territory of Baku, Azerbaijan, a rapidly growing metropolitan city located along the western coast of the Caspian Sea. Baku is characterized by a semi-arid climate, low annual precipitation, high levels of solar radiation, and frequent dust-laden winds, all of which influence the dispersion and deposition of pollutants in the environment.

To assess spatial variability in heavy metal accumulation, sampling sites were deliberately selected to represent contrasting environmental conditions within the city. One of the selected test sites was located within the Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences, situated in a relatively unpolluted zone on the

outskirts of the city. This area is characterized by minimal industrial activity, low vehicular traffic, and well-developed green infrastructure. In contrast, additional sampling plots were established in heavily urbanized districts of Baku that are known for intense traffic congestion, high population density, and proximity to major roads and intersections. These sites were selected based on their exposure to vehicular emissions and urban air pollution (Mammadova A. & Mammadova R., 2019).

The concentrations of selected heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Zn, and Cu) in both soil and leaf samples were measured using the X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometry method, which offers a rapid and efficient means of multi-elemental analysis. The analysis was performed on a "Rigaku NEX QC+" spectrometer (Applied Rigaku Technologies, Japan) (Oladebeye et al., 2020; Mammadova, 2024).

Results and discussion. The concentrations of Zn, Cu, Pb, and Cd in soil samples collected from both the environmental control zone and the environmental risk zone revealed a marked difference in contamination levels (Table 1).

Table 1

Soil samples	Zn(mg/kg)	Cu(mg/kg)	Pb(mg/kg)	Cd(mg/kg)
environmental control zone	47.4	26.3	9.5	1.1
environmental risk zone	297.5	104.1	78.9	3.8

In the control zone, all metal concentrations are within both the MPCs and Clark values, except for Cd, which slightly exceeds its natural background level (Clark = 0.15 mg/kg). In contrast, the environmental risk zone shows significant contamination, with Zn, Cu, Pb, and Cd concentrations exceeding both MPCs and Clark values (Mammadova et al., 2024).

These results clearly indicate strong anthropogenic input, especially near roads with heavy traffic, where vehicle emissions, tire wear, and industrial dust deposition are likely major contributors.

From the table two can be seen that in the control zone, both species contain metal concentrations well

below MPCs, reflecting low environmental exposure. In the environmental risk zone, distinct differences emerge. Cu in *Q. ilex* reaches 98.1 mg/kg, 4.9 times higher than the MPC and significantly more than in *O. europaea* (48.4 mg/kg). Pb in *Q. ilex* is 8.2 mg/kg, exceeding the MPC (5.0 mg/kg), while in *O. europaea* it remains below (3.3 mg/kg). Cd concentrations in both species increase in polluted areas but only in *Q. ilex* (0.60 mg/kg) does it exceed the MPC by 2 times. In *O. europaea*, it remains below. Zn levels are elevated in both species near roads but do not exceed the MPC.

Table 2

Leaf samples	Zn(mg/kg)	Cu(mg/kg)	Pb(mg/kg)	Cd(mg/kg)	
<i>Quercus ilex</i> L.	environmental control zone	29.6	8.6	0.8	0.20
	environmental risk zone	56.5	98.1	8.2	0.60
<i>Olea europaea</i> L.	environmental control zone	25.3	7.2	0.6	0.05
	environmental risk zone	49.1	48.4	3.3	0.20

The results of the present study demonstrate that *Q. ilex* exhibits a higher capacity to accumulate all the investigated heavy metals, particularly copper (Cu) and lead (Pb), in both ecologically clean and polluted environments. This trend highlights the species' heightened sensitivity to urban pollution and supports its suitability as a bioindicator of heavy metal contamination. In com-

parison, *O. europaea* also shows increased metal uptake under conditions of environmental stress; however, the concentrations of Pb, Cd, Zn, and Cu in its leaf tissues remain consistently lower than those observed in *Q. ilex*. This may indicate greater physiological resistance or more restricted translocation of metals from roots to shoots, possibly due to more efficient detoxification or exclusion mechanisms.

Conclusion. The results of this study confirm that urban soils in Baku, particularly near traffic-intensive zones, contain elevated levels of heavy metals, many of which exceed both permissible and natural background concentrations. These elevated soil levels are mirrored in the leaf tissues of local tree species, especially in *Q. ilex*, which accumulates toxic levels of Cu and Pb in polluted zones. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring urban green spaces not only for environmental assessment but also for public health and sustainable landscape planning.

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